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SOCIO-PSYCHOLOGICAL DETERMINANTS OF DEVIANT BEHAVIORAL MANIFESTATIONS

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Abstract: the study of theoretical and scientific sources related to the study of the problem of deviant behavior in adolescents allows us to make more detailed observations about the factors underlying the occurrence of deviant behavior occurring in them. This possibility requires studying the dynamics of aggressive behavior, addictive behavior in adolescents, situations observed in individuals in conflict situations, and taking into account age, gender, and territorial characteristics.

Basic concepts: teenager, manifestations of deviant behavior, age, gender, territorial differences, genetic and biological, social conditions, constitutional conditions, psychological factor and mechanisms.

Relevance: Particular attention is paid to the problem of behavioral deviance and its prevention, which is manifested among minors who do not correspond to the generally accepted, established norms of behavior of society in the modern conditions of reforming the system of personality deviance in the world. One of the important goals of the upbringing, formation of personality is to follow the established norms in society, to structure personal qualities, develop social skills, improve ways to eliminate deviations in behavior, in which the main factors, socio-psychological norm, qualities of morality, issues of the system of interpersonal relations of a teenage personality to people, family, society are studied separately. According to a statement by the World Health Organization (WHO) on the results of 2022, “about 200 thousand murders and robberies are committed annually among aggressive adolescents aged 11-16 around the world, and the identification of the causes of this behavior is being studied by experts around the world as an urgent problem”. On a global scale, special attention is paid to issues related to the study of the psychological causes of deviant behavior among minors, scientific examination of factors and conditions that cause deviant behavior, scientific improvement of methods of psychodiagnostic practice in this matter, as well as the development of preventive measures for obtaining premature deviant behavior, development of social behavior of adolescents in educational institutions, scientific research is being carried out on the implementation of psychoprophylaxis and psychocorrective work, which serves to adequately assess the system of

interpersonal relations. Because, the upbringing of the younger generation, whose behavior is guided by the norm, social life standards, the developed country will always be progressive in all areas.

Currently, decrees, laws, decisions issued by the government, together with legal regulations in the field of modern education, define strategies for educating adolescents so that they can find a clear solution to the problems that arise in their process of social activity. There is some difficulty in the assimilation of changes and reforms in society by members of society, because of which situations are observed in members of society that may apply light, contrary to established procedures for solving the problem. This condition is often prominent in the growing younger generations. Deviant behavior in young people: the main reason for the occurrence of vices such as alcoholism, drug addiction, prostitution, crime is the social environment.

Main part. Focusing on the issue of the psychological involvement of individual, age and gender differences in Deviant behavior manifestations, we can see that this, in turn, is determined in a significant way by individual characteristics, gender differences. For example, it is well known to us that the manifestations of outlaw morality are more a characteristic phenomenon for individuals of the male sex. Even among women in the context of globalization, deviant behavior, despite the increase in crime, its relative indicators are lower than that of men, for example, in Russia in 1998, focusing on the statistics of crime related to women, is 15% of the total criminal cases recorded. And in the case of men of the male sex, we can see that these figures are a little more and are conspicuous in different manifestations.

Even in the conditions of Uzbekistan, it is not possible to turn a blind eye to cases related to various manifestations of crime among minors. This was noted in the data of the statistical agency under the president, which relied on the Ministry of internal affairs, that in 2019-2023 the number of registered crimes increased by 2.3 times—from 46 thousand to 104 thousand. There is a gradual decline following the sharp rise in 2021. At the same time, the number of serious and serious crimes increased throughout the year. Of the 3,599 minors (4% of the 88,913 perpetrators) who committed the crime the previous year, 82.6% were criminalized. Of these, 744 are between the ages of 13-15 and 2,855 are between the ages of 16-17. The proportion of girls was 8.7% — 314 people. Most or 1,602 of the minors by type of offense committed burglary (one year ago — 1,581 persons), 453 were bullied (284 persons, an increase of 60 percent), 135 were fraud (134 persons), 181 were robbed and raided (162 persons,

+11%), 104 committed intentional bodily harm (74, +40%), 54 were attempted to touch and name (46, +20%), 27 — extortion (16.70%) while 12 committed the crime of intentional homicide and attempted manslaughter (10.20%).

In addition to the work carried out by our president in the management of the state and society, special attention is paid to the issues of crime prevention and upbringing, spirituality among minors. In this regard, schools are setting out specific measures aimed at solving problems, working with parents and neighborhood activists of students who have problems with Juvenile Delinquency Prevention, meaningful leisure and vocational guidance, education and education.

We found it necessary to state our opinion as follows, based on the hypothesis that the aggressiveness of adolescents in their personality and its predisposition to aggressive morality are determined in a significant way by its individual development. Many factors are involved in the origin of aggressive ethics, including age, gender, individual characteristics, external physical and social conditions. For example, in an individual, deviance, aggression can be fully developed, potentiated by noise, heat, tightness, environmental problems, meteorological and similar external conditions. However, many researchers of this issue try to explain that the decisive role in the formation of deviant behavior in a person is played by his direct social lifestyle. In our eyes, the individual considers some of the leading factors that call for or support deviant behavior.

Methodology: E.V. Zmanovskaya defines the following groups of factors that determine the deviant behavior of an individual: - external conditions of the physical environment; - external social conditions; - internal, hereditary-biological and constitutional conditions; - personal (psychological) causes and mechanisms of deviant behavior. In our opinion, the study of socio-psychological determinants of the manifestation of deviant behavior in adolescents when it is recommended to start with social factors in the first place. In these processes, of course, positive results are noted in the processes associated with the work of the adolescent personality with factors leading to deviance, the observance of the norms of social life of children with deviant behavior on the basis of conducting correctional work.

In general, for the development of the personality of a child and a teenager, aggression is not visible, its result and the incorrect reaction of those around him are dangerously affected. When violence gives attention, authoritarianism, recognition, money, other advantages, in the case of children and adolescents, a

socially functioning and structured morality based on large people (for example, criminal groups) is formed, which is most likely based on the culture of power. Attempts by those around them to suppress aggression by force lead to the opposite expected effect in most situations.

The manifestation of deviant behavior in older people, their appearance is much more diverse, since most often these processes are determined by their individual characteristics. As Individual-personal descriptions, potentiating aggressive morals are usually also viewed as sabous situations, such as public disapproval, skepticism, superstitious habits (such as national), as well as not shortening this feeling instead of being ashamed of sinfulness, not admitting the guilt they have committed. An important role in supporting a tendency to violence can be played by a person's belief in his own fate (and sometimes the fate of other people as well) as the fact that he is considered the sole governor, as well as his positive attitude towards aggression (useful or normative appearance).

It is possible to talk about people in a separate category - extremists who demonstrate aggression, or more often, or in the final form. Extremists, in turn, are clearly divided into two groups: with low and high self-control. While the former consistently exhibit aggression in the strength of weakly developed self-control mechanisms, those in the second group-even long-term abstinence from strong lambs-exhibit final manifestations of aggression (up to brutal) once internal resources are depleted.

Another characteristic that affects the deviant behavior of an individual is its ability to tolerate frustration. It is known that under frustration is understood a situation called by the barriers to satisfaction of the need or the path to achieving the goal. Some authors consider frustration as one of the leading causes of aggressive ethics. Frustration in general is a very common sight and these people differ greatly in their ability to handle it. If aggressive morality is successfully helped to eliminate frustration, then in accordance with the laws of education it will be strengthened in great probability. Also, if a person is highly susceptible to frustration, then again, a problem may arise if socially acceptable ways to overcome frustration have not been developed.

In the manifestation of Deviant behavior - if we evaluate the sexual (gender) factor, - then teenage boys show much higher direct and physical, and teenage girls-indirect and verbal aggression. In general, at the same time, when teenage girls often and successfully resort to its psychological variant, a great predisposition to the use of physical force on the male sex is noted.

Despite the entire importance of age, gender and individual factors, in the formation of aggressive ethics, according to many researchers, social conditions in the development of personality are of leading importance. The influence of the media (media) on the personality deviant behavior can be considered one of the most controversial issues. Proponents of the negative impact of the media come from the argument that people learn to behave aggressively, first of all, by observing the aggression of others. M.Hewsmann observed the reciprocity between television viewing and aggression with a team of researchers over a period of 20 years. Through social networks, which are now growing, we can see that under the influence of azart games aimed at poisoning the consciousness of young people, their spiritual world, adolescents show conflicts in the system of family relations, the disappearance of mutual respect in the system of interpersonal relations, manifestations of aggressive behavior. The mechanism of formation of deviant behavior in adolescents can be seen in the following image: TV show, azart games, a feeling of interest in shots with scenes of savagery - aggressive fantasies - impersonation with a character, mastering an aggressive way of solving a problem and influencing people, repeating aggressive actions, using aggression to solve a problem in interpersonal relationships are recorded in situations such as In general, the reaction of people to stage performances, which are characterized by aggressive scenes, violent situations, can be varied: disgusting, unpleasant, virtualization (perception of the described phenomenon in a non-standard quality), only in some cases - such as admiring or striving for imitation can be conspicuous.

As a factor influencing the deviant behavior of the adolescent personality, we can see that the influence of the social environment of the family remains the main social resource in the formation of aggressive morality in the individual. It is well known that aggression is manifested not only in relation to enemies strangers or opponents. Psychological or physical exertion is not an absolutely rare phenomenon for most families. The forms of manifestations of aggressive states in families are diverse. These can be direct physical or sexual abuse, coldness, bullying, negative assessment, pressure on the individual, non-focusing on the adolescent individual, not receiving the child emotionally, and several other crusading situations like this.

Family members can show aggressive morals in themselves or provide encouragement to an unwanted act of the child, such as encouraging punching, pride in his victory, ridiculing the little ones of himself, inducing him to show "I",

creating visions of deviant behavior in his teenage personality without being directly aware of themselves.

Conclusions and analysis: thus, aggressive morality is a fairly typical sight for children and adolescents. In addition, in the process of socialization of the individual, aggressive morality performs a number of important functions. Aggression in moderation frees the individual from fear, helps to protect their own interests, protects against external danger, promotes adaptation. In this regard, it is possible to talk about two types of aggression: harmless-manifested in adapted and destructive - not adapted manifestations.

The study of the problem of Deviant behavior is directly visible not only in adolescent boys, but also in negative situations that are observed in the activities of adolescent girls. Based on the observed experiments, it can be concluded that criminogenic crimes, characteristic of women or men, may differ from one another for some time. Deviations such as infanticide, escape from home, foxholding, shoplifting are often committed by teenage girls. Teenage boys, on the other hand, often have a high incidence of car hijacking, raiding, burglary, inappropriate touching, bodily injury, and performing criminal acts related to manslaughter.

The age factor determines the specific ethics at different stages of ontogenesis. The dynamics of age-related characteristics of the lawlessness, deviant behavior are noticeable as follows:

- most crimes are observed between 25 and 35 years of age;
- the amount of crime will grow from 14 to 29 years old without any words;
- in most cases, the commission of a crime is 29 years old;
- There is a slow decline between the ages of 29 and 40;
- After 40, making a crime becomes sparse.

Obviously, anti-social behavior can be spoken of only after reaching a certain age. It is not before the age of 6-8 that a small child can not adequately understand his morality, control it and social norms. Only in school will the child for the first time and really collide with principled social requirements, and from this school age it will be possible to expect the child to strictly follow the Basic Rules of morality.

In the early stage of ontogenesis, a violation of social morality reflects problems in the child's psychic development or a nervous reaction with a character that passes from generation to generation. For example, a child's theft at the age of five can be associated with hyperphobicity, an eternal need for attention and

love, a reaction to the loss of a loved one, a cessation in intellectual development, the impossibility of obtaining the necessary nutrients and items.

Thus, the interest in aggressive behavior under the negative influence of internal and external socio-psychological factors becomes, indeed, bad forms of deviant behavior, and this can go from robust destructive behavior to forms dangerous to society. We can also say that aggression in moderation has a protective character and serves to lead a life. At the same time, it appears as a source of activity of the individual, its creative potential and striving for achievements, manifested in a socio-personal position.

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